

APPLICATION OF FOCUSED ION BEAM AND PLASMA TREATMENTS TO POLYURETHANE SCAFFOLDS FOR TISSUE ENGINEERING

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SUMMARY

To mimic structural and functional features of extracellular matrix, we applied FIB and O₂ plasma treatments to PU substrates. FIB treatment induced formation of nano-scale wrinkles on PU surface. O₂ plasma treatment induced even distribution of adsorbed proteins on PU surface from culturing media. Both treatments enhanced cell adhesion and growth.

Keywords: Focused ion beam; Plasma treatment; Tissue engineering; Polyurethane; Fibroblast

INTRODUCTION

The extracellular matrix (ECM) is a complex structural entity surrounding and supporting cells that are found within mammalian tissues. It provides structural support and anchorage to human cells, regulates intercellular communication and activates various cellular functions by sequestering cellular growth factors. Thus, formation of the ECM is essential for processes like cell growth and wound healing. Having wrinkles, pores, fibers and pits with sizes ranging from several tens to hundreds of nanometers [1], the ECM is composed of interlocking meshes of fibrous proteins such as collagen and elastin, and glycosaminoglycans, such as proteoglycan and hyaluronic acid, and other functional proteins, such as fibronectin and laminin.

One of the key issues in current tissue engineering is the physical mimicry of ECM so that adhesion, spreading, migration, orientation and proliferation of cells are enhanced during in vitro or in vivo study. To mimic morphological characterization of the ECM, various methods such as photolithography [2-3], X-ray lithography [4-5], electron-beam lithography [6-7], electropolishing, and sandblasting [8] have been applied to polymers, ceramics and metals. The abovementioned methods have shown two serious limitations in mimicking ECM: Firstly, in general, most of these methods created repeating regular patterns. Although structural complexity is required for the ECM-mimicking scaffolds, majority of the studies adopted regular patterned grooves and ridges to control dimensions and shapes [2-7, 9-12] which caused the cells to spread and orient along the patterned grooves due to contact guidance. Secondly, these methods require time-consuming steps to fabricate the surface patterns. For example, a photolithographic process is performed by the following steps; coating of a polymeric resist on a substrate,

irradiation through a mask, immersion of the resist-coated substrate in the developer to make a positive-tone or negative-tone image, etching of the substrate not covered by resist and finally, removal of the residual resist.

In this study, to overcome these limitations, we applied the focused ion beam (FIB) process to physically mimic the complex patterns of ECM. The FIB process allowed us to create wrinkles of various types such as straight, herringbone, and hierarchical modes, and sizes ranging from several tens to hundreds of nanometers on a polymeric substrate in just one step [13-14]. Polyurethane (PU) was chosen as the polymeric substrate because PU is well known for its bio- and blood-compatibility, good mechanical properties and versatility [15-17]. Because fibroblasts have a propensity to adhere to hydrophilic surfaces [18-20], O₂ plasma treatment has been applied to the FIB-treated PU substrate to increase surface wettability. To verify cell growth on the PU substrates, human skin fibroblasts were used.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Substrate Fabrication

1.1. Materials

Bio-grade PU (Pellethane) was purchased from Dow chemical (USA). N,N-Dimethylformamide (DMF) and tetrahydrofuran (THF) were purchased from Samchun chemical (Korea) and used as received.

1.2. Preparation of PU substrates

PU solution (11wt%) was made by dissolving PU in DMF/THF (7/3 (w/w)). Solvent casting method was used to obtain 8.5mm X 8.5mm and 100µm thick PU films. To remove residual solvents, PU substrates were placed in a vacuum oven at room temperature for 3days and boiled in water for 2hours. Four types of PU substrate samples were produced; control PU substrates (PU), O₂ plasma-treated (PU+PL), FIB-treated (PU+FIB), and FIB and O₂ plasma-treated (PU+FIB+PL) PU samples. FIB treatments were performed using a FE-SEM/FIB dual-beam system (NOVA 200; FEI, Hillsboro, OR, USA) with a 30kV Ga⁺ ion beam with ion fluence of 6.25 X 10¹³ ions/cm². The modified area by one scan was 1mm X 1.35mm and about 45 scans were applied to each sample. O₂ plasma treatments were performed using low temperature and low pressure-type Labplasma (Europlasma, Belgium) with a gas flow rate of 100sccm for 10minutes.

2. Characterization of Substrates

To study the morphology of the PU substrates, SEM was used. AFM was also used to obtain the topographical images of samples. To verify the surface modification by O₂ plasma treatment, water contact angles of the samples were calculated using the sessile drop method.

3. Cell Experiments

3.1. Cell culture

Human skin fibroblasts were extracted and subcultured with DMEM media at 37°C

and 5% CO₂. After the secondary passage, 3.0 X 10⁴ cells were carefully added to each well which contained PU substrates and were cultured for 1, 3, 5 and 7 days at 37°C and 5% CO₂. Fresh culturing medium was added every three days.

3.2. Cell adhesion and proliferation assay

To verify cell growth, fluorescent microscopy and MTT assay were used. For fluorescent microscopy, Croscope Inverte (Olympus) equipped with a digital camera was used. For the MTT assay, after staining of live cells, cell counting was performed using ELISA plate reader with a test wavelength of 570nm and a reference wavelength of 630nm.

3.3. Characterization of the cell morphology

After dehydrating the cell/substrate complexes and sputter-coating with platinum, SEM images were obtained to characterize the cell morphology on the PU substrates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Morphologies of PU Substrates

Figure 1. A photograph (a) and SEM images (b)-(d) of FIB-treated PU substrate.

Figure 1 shows SEM images of a FIB-treated PU sample. Wrinkles of straight and herringbone-like modes are clearly identified. The herringbone-like form is more

similar to the actual morphology of ECM. Unfortunately, even with high resolution, 2-D SEM images failed to detect the effect of O₂ plasma treatment on the morphological changes of PU substrates. Therefore, to clarify the topographies of O₂ plasma treated PU substrates, we obtained AFM images which are given in Figure 2. The O₂ plasma treated PU substrates definitely shows smoother surfaces comparing figures (a) to (b) and (e) to (g). This might be the result of surface etching which is required for O₂ plasma treatment. From the results, we verified that FIB treatment can create ECM-like surface morphology and O₂ plasma treatment can reduce surface roughness.

Figure 2. AFM images of PU (a), PU+PL (b), PU+FIB (c)-(f) and PU+FIB+PL (g).

2. Effect of O₂ Plasma Treatment on the Surface Wettability of PU Substrates

Figure 3. Images of water drops on PU substrate before O₂ plasma treatment (a) and after (b) O₂ plasma treatment.

As shown in Figure 3, the surface wettability of PU substrates considerably increased after O₂ plasma treatment. Average contact angles of control PU samples and FIB-treated PU samples were $81.26 \pm 0.34^\circ$ and $81.38 \pm 0.86^\circ$, respectively. And those of O₂ plasma-treated PU samples and samples treated with both methods were $15.24 \pm 0.78^\circ$ and $15.40 \pm 0.78^\circ$, respectively. Interestingly, FIB treatment did not affect the surface wettability and this might be explained by the sparse FIB-treated regions. Around 30% of the surface of FIB treated PU substrate had nano-scale wrinkles. Because surface wettability is dependent on many parameters in addition to morphology, such as surface energy and existence of functional groups, further studies are needed to assess current results. Nonetheless, considering the above results, O₂ plasma treatment enhanced the surface wettability by creating hydrophilic functional groups such as carboxylic acid and hydrogen bonding.

3. Cell Growth on the Surfaces of PU Substrates

Figure 4. Fluorescent images of human skin fibroblasts on (a) PU, day 1; (b) PU, day 7; (c) PU+PL, day 1; (d) PU+PL, day 7; (e) PU+FIB, day 1; (f) PU+FIB, day 7; (g) PU+FIB+PL, day 1; (h) PU+FIB+PL, day 7.

As shown in Figure 4, diverse aspects of cell adhesion, spreading and proliferation were observed on the PU substrates. At day 1, cultured fibroblasts on the non-treated

PU surface (Figure 4(a)) did not yet spread. However, on the surface-treated samples (Figure 4(c), 4(e), and 4(g)), cells were well adhered and spread out. It is noteworthy that fibroblasts tended to primarily adhere to the surface-modified regions of FIB treated samples. Taking FIB-treated PU substrates into account, fibroblasts hardly adhered to the non-treated region (elliptical area of Figure 4(e)). Meanwhile, on the both FIB and O₂ plasma-treated PU surface, cells adhered and spread out even on the non-FIB-treated region. A possible explanation for this phenomenon could be the increase in the amount of adsorbed proteins, such as fibronectin and vitronectin, from the culturing media due to the capillary effect of FIB-treated regions and enhanced surface wettability by O₂ plasma treatment [19-22]. As shown in Figure 4(b), 4(d), and 4(h), at day 7, cultured fibroblasts proliferated well over the entire surface area of the PU substrates except for PU+FIB. As for PU+FIB, since the fibroblasts showed a tendency to adhere only to the FIB-treated area, a relatively small area seemed to have been available for cell proliferation resulting in cluster formation.

Figure 5. Result of MTT assay of the PU samples.

The results of MTT assay shown in Figure 5 evidently indicate that a synergy between FIB-treatment and O₂ plasma-treatment on cell proliferation exists. At day 7, overgrowth of fibroblasts on the surface-treated PU substrates resulted in cell death due to contact inhibition. On the other hand, fibroblasts on the surface of non-treated PU substrates still show steady proliferation.

CONCLUSIONS

To mimic structural features of natural ECM, we applied FIB and O₂ plasma treatments to PU substrates. Both treatments enabled PU substrates to adsorb more proteins from the culture medium. However, FIB treatment induced formation of cell clusters resulting in faster cell death due to contact inhibition. O₂ plasma treatment induced even distribution of fibroblasts on the surface of PU substrates by increasing surface wettability. Therefore, synergistic effect will be expected if fine control of both treatments is applied to tissue engineering.

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